

ALTIMETRY IN THE GULF OF MEXICO: AN EXAMINATION OF ERS-1 AND TOPEX/POSEIDON

Donald R. Johnson
Naval Research Laboratory, Code 7332
Stennis Space Center, Ms 39529

Abstract. Over the past year, sea surface height anomaly data from both ERS-1 and Topex/Poseidon altimeters have been posted on a science bulletin board in a unique program to rapidly disseminate data among workers in the Gulf of Mexico. Other contributions to this board from a variety of data sources such as Argos tracked drifters and frontal analysis from AVHRR have enabled good comparisons. Operational time scale submission to the bulletin board imposes a difficult set of requirements, especially with respect to the altimetric reference surface. In this study we have investigated the use of a single "flat" track as a reference. Comparisons are made for the Loop Current and its rings and for altimetry in near coastal areas.

Loop Current and Rings

The Gulf of Mexico is a semi-enclosed sea with a variety of circulation features as interesting and as complex as those found in the major ocean basins. Two dominating features are the Loop Current (hereafter, LC), a component of the North Atlantic's western boundary current, and large anticyclonic rings, shed from the LC. Trade wind currents of the North Atlantic consolidate as they pass northwestward through the Caribbean, reaching the intensity of a western boundary current at the Yucatan Peninsula. Ingress of this flow into the Gulf is through the relatively narrow Yucatan Straits. At times the flow penetrates deeply (figure 1) into the northeastern Gulf before looping anticyclonically and returning southward to exit the Gulf through the entrance to the Florida Straits between Cuba and the Florida Keys. During these times of vigorous inflow, the LC may

fold back upon itself, and pinch off into a separate anticyclone (ring). The remainder of the LC reattaches itself south of the newly formed ring and continues on a more direct path into the Florida Straits. Although formation and subsequent breakoff of the rings occur on the eastern side of the Gulf, the rings make a major impact on marine activities throughout the basin. After the rings detach from the LC, they migrate into the western basin and break up against the Mexican/Texas shelf. Just as the LC tends to dominate the eastern basin, rings and their breakup components tend to dominate the western basin. Interactions with shelf water and smaller cyclones, spawned around the edges of the main anticyclone, give interest and importance to the rings.

It had previously been thought that an annual cycle occurred in the LC, with stronger inflow and penetration into the Gulf taking place each spring, followed by breakup of the extended loop into an anticyclone. More recently, it has been recognized that ring shedding occurs on an irregular basis at intervals of 6-12 months, with an average of about 10 months. Numerical modeling has shown that the LC becomes dynamically unstable and sheds rings, regardless of changes in inflow rate (Hurlburt and Thompson, 1980). Part of the difficulty that we have had in the past in recognizing the time scales of ring shedding and ring motion has come from the difficulties of observing these large (300-500 km diameter), highly variable features from standard shipboard surveys. AVHRR has provided a substantial degree of improvement in monitoring capability, and indeed brought our first recognition that the cycle was not seasonal, and that migration into the

Figure 1: AVHRR image of the Gulf of Mexico on 18 April 1993 showing strong intrusion of the Loop Current. Topex/Poseidon and ERS-1 altimeter tracks are shown which captured this intrusion (see text). The ERS-1 track has the greatest inclination.

western Gulf was a fundamental characteristic of the rings. But cloud cover and summer temperature masking (weak difference in temperature between the rings and ambient Gulf water) reduce the effectiveness of AVHRR.

Within the past decade, satellite altimetry has become an important monitoring tool for the Gulf. In contrast to AVHRR, it has the ability to penetrate cloud cover and is not dependent on sea surface temperature contrasts, making it an excellent candidate for operational monitoring. There are many difficulties, however, in achieving that goal. Offshore industries, who are major contributors to the economies of the Gulf states, are vitally interested in an ability to monitor the principal features in the Gulf.

Operational Monitoring

As part of an extensive, multi-year field and modeling study of the Gulf of Mexico, sponsored by the Mineral's Management Service (MMS), near-real-time altimetry is being posted at weekly intervals by electronic mail on a science bulletin board. The objective of this posting has been to examine the utility of altimetry in an operational setting for design of ongoing field studies as well as for aid to industries engaged in offshore activities. Excellent feedback from other components of the program create an opportunity to compare the accuracy of near-real-time altimeter observations. This paper discusses the altimeter product and some of the difficulties and solutions that are currently being applied.

The bulletin board, Omnet/Gulf.Mex, was established as a means of rapid communication among scientists, managers and the marine industry using recently acquired data. Publication on this board, in specified formats, of cruise tracks, station and mooring locations, Argos drifter tracks, frontal locations and sea surface height (SSH) from altimetry (among other types of data) can be obtained easily by the community of investigators working in the Gulf. To display this data, a basic-language program has been written for the PC and disseminated by MMS. Options in the software allow graphic display of the outline of the Gulf of Mexico, gridded with longitude and latitude. Data downloaded from the bulletin board then can be displayed over this map of the Gulf, compared with other forms of data and interpreted in terms of operational requirements. Figure 2 shows an example of the product that can be obtained in this fashion. Satellite altimetry and

frontal locations are displayed together. In this instance, the altimetry came from the Naval Research Laboratory-Stennis Space Center and the frontal location was supplied by the Louisiana State University's Coastal Studies Institute. The frontal positions were taken from the same AVHRR imagery shown in figure 1 and the altimetry was taken over one week surrounding the date of the imagery. There is a good correspondence between the frontal position which describes the LC and the high SSH topography from altimetry. There are indications of problems elsewhere, however - notably the slope region of the Campeche Banks off the north coast of the Yucatan Peninsula. In this location there are relatively sharp changes in SSH which are not connected with known current systems. The coincidence between the SSH anomalies in this region and the location of the slope are indicative of problems with the altimetric reference surface.

Figure 2: Example of combined products from the Omnet/Gulf.Mex bulletin board as displayed on a PC. The circles are SSH values from Topex/Poseidon for 7 days surrounding 18 April, 1993. Light circles are negative, dark circles are positive anomalies. Lines in the background represent locations of strong thermal contrast (frontal analysis) from imagery shown in figure 1.

Altimetric Reference Surface

Since the radar altimeter measures the actual sea level with respect to a reference earth ellipsoid, it incorporates the marine geoid as well as dynamic topography associated with ocean currents. Spatial variations in the marine geoid are one to two orders of magnitude larger than spatial variations in dynamic topography, making it difficult to properly separate the two. A common technique simply averages all passes along a repeat track and takes the difference of each pass from the average. This technique removes mean dynamic topography along with the non-temporally varying marine geoid, and depends for its success on temporally variable SSH. It is common to

Figure 3: Time sequence of T/P passes along track shown in figure 1, referenced to the Rapp Mean. Earliest pass is on bottom, progressing upward at about 10 day intervals.

average over an entire year so that seasonal variations are included in the residual. This long averaging period, however, is not possible for operational efforts where the desire is for immediate application of the data.

Reference surfaces have also been made using data from previous altimeters. The Marsh Mean is an older reference surface in common use, and the Rapp Mean is a more recent reference surface which uses altimetry from GEOSAT-ERM. Subtracting either of these reference surfaces from near-real-time data eliminates much of the marine geoid from the altimeter pass. Figure 3 shows the sequence of Topex/Poseidon passes associated with the track shown in figure 1. These passes took place during a period of strong intrusion of the LC into the northern Gulf. From figure 3, it is easy to distinguish a rise in SSH topography at about 26°N. This rise is associated with the intruding LC. But it is also possible to see many features which do not change with time, such as the 2 m anomaly at about 24°N. A closer examination showed that this anomaly is associated with the steep continental slope region of the Campeche Banks. North of 28°N (figure 3), several smaller non-varying anomalies occur. These latter anomalies occur over the northeastern continental shelf and slope, again indicating problems with the reference surface where large bathymetric gradients (and marine geoid gradients) exist. Clearly part of the problem comes from inadequate coverage by previous altimeters which formed the reference surface.

For an operational situation, the requirement exists for an immediately available reference surface which is relatively flat with respect to the dynamic topography. In a simple effort to investigate the use of a single pass for a reference surface, the variance of a set of T/P passes were obtained after the Rapp Mean surface had been removed. Of the fourteen T/P tracks that are being used in the Gulf of Mexico program, ten had sufficiently small variation in the first 3 cycles (20 days) to be used as immediate references.

Figure 4 is a repeat of the T/P passes presented in figure 3, but showing the results of simply using one of these early passes as a reference rather than a pre-determined mean. The anomalous behavior is clearly removed over the sharp bathymetry, and the intrusion of the LC clearly stands out. Figure 5 shows similar results for the ERS-1 track (figure 1). Again movement of the LC is clearly distinguishable.

If the common method of averaging all passes along one track were used, then the LC would first appear as an anomalous low feature and could be interpreted as a cyclone. Toward the end of the period, it would be interpreted as a SSH

high, or anticyclone, but with low amplitude. The present method of using an early pass as reference means, of course, that any anomalous feature in the reference would latter show as its opposite.

Acknowledgement: This program is sponsored by Mineral's Management Service under the Gulf of Mexico Basin Scale Modeling Project.

Reference: Hurlburt, H.E. and J.D. Thompson, A numerical study of Loop Current intrusions and eddy shedding, *J. Phys. Oceanogr.*, 10, 1611-1651, 1980.

Figure 4: Same as figure 3 but using the first pass as the reference.

Figure 5: Same as figure 3 but using ERS-1 at about 35 day intervals and using the first pass as a reference.